

DESIGN, CONSTRUCTION AND PERFORMANCE TEST OF A MANUAL TIMBER SAWING MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the Design, Construction and Performance Test of a Manual Timber Sawing Machine. It does not require any specific input energy or electric power. In this paper, human power plays a vital role. This paper consists of a larger sprocket that rotates with the help of human powered pedal. The smaller sprocket is connected to the plane which is mutually perpendicular to the axis of the larger sprocket is rotated by using a chain drive. The smaller sprocket is rigidly supported by means of shaft and bearing support. The circular saw is mounted on the same shaft where the smaller sprocket is mounted. When the pedal is operated, a circular saw is rotated which in turn cuts the wooden block material. The main aim is to reduce the human effort for machining various materials such as wooden blocks etc.

The power circular saw machine, which runs on human power, works on the principle of the conversion of rotational motion in a mutually perpendicular axis. The importance of this paper lies in the very fact that it is green paper and helps us to reduce our electricity needs too. Secondly, this cutter can be used and transferred to our working place easily. Moreover, this paper is very effective for electric power saving in rural areas where there is no electricity

Keywords: Timber Machine, Sprocket

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, we know that, the machining operations are essential for doing successful engineering jobs. We find the machining operations like drilling, grinding, cutting, sawing etc. For performing these operations, we have use different type of machines at different places, which consume lot of time and electricity. In the rural area, electricity cut-off is a major problem which causes discontinuity of work progress. Before three to four decades, when there is unavailability of electricity for working of different machines viz. cutting, grinding, drilling, sawing etc. they used a manual hack saw for cutting a wood or they used an axe to cut a wood which was a very laborious task for humans and consumes a very much power. But in last decades the use of an electric equipment has increased for such an operation which is also not affordable for a small industry or a domestic wood cutting purpose. The used of an electrically power wood cutting and grinding machine consumes electric power as well as cost of operation of machines much more. Then we tried to invent a machine which will be consumed less human power to perform more work[1].

Sawing is one of the most important machining operations in our engineering life. Sawing machine is a device for cutting up bars of material or for cutting out shapes in plates of raw material. The cutting tools of sawing machines may be thin metallic disks with teeth on their edges, thin metal blades or flexible bands with teeth on one edge, or thin grinding wheels. The tools may use any of three actions in sawing: true cutting, grinding, or friction-created melting[2].

Now like all of materials wood is a very useful material for our life. We need to use wood in our daily life for different purposes. For using wood in those purposes, we need to cut or saw wood object or timber by sawing machining operation. That sawing operation is performed with a timber sawing machine. To run this machine,

we need power. Maximum timber sawing machine is run by electric power. But the attention is to save the electric power because it is very costly and in rural area it is not available everywhere. So, we need to utilize human power to save the electricity. So human powered timber sawing machine is need to be constructed.

We need to use human power to run a manual timber sawing machine. But we need to construct such a machine that consumes less human energy to give more output. We can operate this machine by pedal.

Pedal power is the transfer of energy from a human source using a foot pedal and crank system. This technology is most commonly used for transportation and has been used to propel bicycles forever a hundred years. Less commonly pedal power is used to power agricultural and hand tools and even to generate electricity. Some applications include pedal powered laptops, pedal powered grinders and pedal powered water wells. Some third world development papers currently transform used bicycles into pedal powered tools for sustainable development. This paper concentrates on pedal powered saw machining. An individual can generate four times more power by pedaling than by hand-cranking. At the rate of $\frac{1}{4}$ HP, continuous pedaling can be served for only short periods, approximately 10 minutes. However, pedaling at half this power ($\frac{1}{8}$ HP) can be sustained for close to 60 minutes but power capability can depend upon age. Because of the brainstorming exercise, it was apparent that the primary function of pedal power one specific product was particularly useful: the bicycle. Many devices can be run right away with mechanical energy[3].

1.1 Sawing Machine

Sawing machine, device for cutting up bars of material or for cutting out shapes in plates of raw material. The cutting tools of sawing machines may be thin metallic disks with teeth on their edges, thin metal blades or flexible bands with teeth on one edge, or thin grinding wheels. The tools may use any of three actions in sawing: true cutting, grinding, or friction-created melting.

The power hacksaw machine provides a vise for clamping the work and means for reciprocating a U-shaped frame on which is mounted a straight steel hacksaw blade that cuts when moving in one direction only. The saw presses down on the work during the cutting stroke but is raised clear of the work during the return stroke.

The band saw employs an endless flexible steel band with teeth on one edge; the band is carried on two large-diameter rotating wheels mounted on parallel axes some distance apart. Band saws that cut vertically are particularly suitable for cutting out shapes in thin, flat plates from work pieces that lie on horizontal tables.

Cold-sawing machines with toothed disk cutters are used extensively in steel-rolling mills and in places where large quantities of bars are cut. A V-shaped clamping vise enables bundles of bars to be clamped and cut at one time.

Friction-sawing machines are used largely for cutting off steel structural shapes such as I beam channels, and angles. The cutting wheels, with or without teeth, rotate at such high speeds that the heat from the friction of contact is sufficient to remove the metal by melting it. Abrasive cutoff saws, thin rubber or Bakelite-bonded abrasive wheels that are operated at high peripheral speeds, are particularly suitable for cutting off thin tubes and hardened steel bars[2].

1.2 Saw

A saw is a tool consisting of a tough blade, wire, or chain with a hard-toothed edge. It can be called a multipoint cutting tool. It is used to cut through material, very often wood though sometimes metal or stone. Large number of teeth move through the work piece. Feed is given either to the saw or the work piece. The cut is made by placing the toothed edge against the material and moving it forcefully forth and less forcefully back or continuously forward. This force may be applied by hand, or powered by steam, water, electricity or other power source. An abrasive saw has a powered circular blade designed to cut through metal or ceramic[4].

1.3 Types of Saws

The Sawing Machines are classified as:

2.3.1 Reciprocating saw (Power Hacksaw)

1. Horizontal sawing machine

2. Vertical sawing machine

2.3.2 Band saws

1. Contour band saw

2. Friction band saw

2.3.3 Circular saws

1. Cold saw

2. Friction disc

3. Abrasive disc

1.3.1 Reciprocating Saw (Power Hacksaw)

A reciprocating saw is a type of machine-powered saw in which the cutting action is achieved through a push and pull motion of the blade. This type of saw is commonly applied to a type of saw used in construction and demolition work. This type of saw also known as a hognose, Sawzall has a large blade resembling that of a jigsaw and a handle oriented to allow the saw to be used comfortably on vertical surfaces. The typical design of this saw has a foot at the base of the blade, similar to that of a jigsaw. The user holds or rests this foot on the surface being cut so that the tendency of the blade to push away from or pull towards the cut as the blade travels through its movement can be countered[4].

Designs range widely in power, speed, and features, from less powerful portable, handheld models that are usually shaped like a cordless drill, to high-power, high-speed, corded models designed for heavy construction and demolition work. Modern reciprocating saws almost all have variable speed, either through trigger sensitivity or through a dial. Another feature that has become important to the way these saws are used is the inclusion of an orbital action. This action consists of oscillating the traversed reciprocation in up and down fashion (perpendicular to the motion of cut) causing the tip of the blade to move in an oval pattern, up and down as well as back and forth. This feature is primarily for wood, allowing quick cuts[4].

The reciprocating saw is a popular tool used by many window fitters, construction workers and emergency rescue services. Variants and accessories are available for specialized uses, such as clamps and long blades for cutting large pipe[4].

Blades are available for a variety of materials and uses. Common types include metal cutting blades, wood cutting blades, blades for composites, for drywall, and other materials. Many of these blade types have a variety of tooth designs intended for special purposes, such as tree-limb cutting, demolition work, clean cutting, or contaminated materials. Abrasive coated blades are also available for hard materials like tile and stone[4].

A reciprocating saw is also called a hacksaw when it accepts both Hackzall and Sawzall style blades. The term reciprocating saw (also oscillating saw) is also applied generically to any saw which cuts with a back and forth motion. These include:

1. Jigsaw

2. Scroll saw

3. Sabre saw

4. Rotary reciprocating saw

Powered reciprocating tools are also found in surgery and dental surgery, where they are used in operations that require cutting or grinding of bone [4].

It consists of saw frame (Means for reciprocating the saw and frames), Work table and vice, Supporting base, Source of power. Most of the operations are hydraulically controlled. Both square and angular cuts can be made operation of reciprocating saw .Machine drives a blade back and forth through a work piece, pressing down on the cutting stroke and releasing the pressure on the return [6].

Fig 1.1: Reciprocating Saw

1.3.2 Band Saws

A band saw (also written band saw) is a saw with a long, sharp blade consisting of a continuous band of toothed metal stretched between two or more wheels to cut material. They are used principally in woodworking, metalworking, and lumbering, but may cut a variety of materials. Advantages include uniform cutting action as a result of an evenly distributed tooth load, and the ability to cut irregular or curved shapes like a jigsaw. The minimum radius of a curve is determined by the width of the band. Most band saws have two wheels rotating in the same plane, one of which is powered, although some may have three or four to distribute the load. The blade itself can come in a variety of sizes and tooth pitches (teeth per inch, or TPI), which enables the machine to be highly versatile and able to cut a wide variety of materials including wood, metal and plastic [4].

Two types of band saw are very important. Those are

1. Contour Band Saw: It works may be fed in any direction on the table. The direction of feed is readily controlled and changed while cutting is in process.
2. Friction Band Saw: The dull blade produces great friction and the kerfs of the teeth removes small, softened particles of the work [6].

Fig 1.2: Band Saw

1.3.3 Circular Saws

A circular saw is a power-saw using a toothed or abrasive disc or blade to cut different materials using a rotary motion spinning around an arbor. A hole saw and ring saw also use a rotary motion but are different from a circular saw. Circular saws may also be loosely used for the blade itself [4].

A circular saw is a tool for cutting many materials such as wood, masonry, plastic, or metal and may be hand-held or mounted to a machine. In woodworking the term "circular saw" refers specifically to the hand-held type and the table saw and chop saw are other common forms of circular saws. "Skill saw" has become a generic trademark for conventional hand-held circular saws. Circular saw blades are specially designed for each particular material they are intended to cut and in cutting wood are specifically designed for making rip-cuts, cross-cuts, or a combination of both. Circular saws are commonly powered by electricity, but may be powered by a gasoline engine or a hydraulic motor which allows it to be fastened to heavy equipment, eliminating the need for a separate energy source. [4]

There are many kinds of circular saw. Some of those are:

1. Cold Saw: It has a circular blade with inserted teeth and also large diameter blades. By rapid saw we can cut very rapidly. It runs at relatively slow speed but very powerful. The average thickness of cut is 6mm. [6]
2. Friction Disk Saw: Its circular blades having almost no teeth. It runs very high speed. It also generates heat. Metal is removed by heat of friction. It leaves a heavier burr and less accurate surface. [6]
3. Abrasive Saw: Rubber bonded wheels rotating at high speed used. Its cutting action is fast and accurate. [6]

Fig 1.3: Circular Saw

1.4 Manual Timber Sawing Machine. (Pedal Power)

Manual timber sawing machine is a type of machine which will run by the transfer of energy from a human source. The machine can be pedal powered or hand operated. But in our machine, we will transfer energy from human source by pedaling. The principle of pedal power timber sawing machine is to change circulatory motion or cycling motion into translator motion with the help of cutting rod. This is mainly used for cutting metals, plastics and woods. It is manually pedal operated system.

1.5 Pedal Power Operation of circular saw

The principle of pedal power Circular saw is to change circulatory motion into translator motion with the help of metal cutting rod. It is manually operating system by human source. If we use dynamo then we can produce electricity which will be help to lighting the work piece area when electricity is not available in mechanical workshop. Hand-held Circular saws consist of a metal arch with a handle, usually a pistol grip, with pins for attaching a narrow disposable blade. A screw or other mechanism is used to put the thin blade under Tension. It is a fine tooth hand saw with a blade under tension. Different TPI is needed for different jobs of cutting [3].

1.6 Circular Saw Blade

A circular saw is a power-saw using a toothed or abrasive disc or blade to cut different materials using a rotary motion spinning around an arbor. A hole saw and ring saw also use a rotary motion but are different from a circular saw. Circular saws may also be loosely used for the blade itself. Circular saws were invented in the late 18th century and were in common use in sawmills in the United States by the middle of the 19th century.

A circular saw is a tool for cutting many materials such as wood, masonry, plastic, or metal and may be hand-held or mounted to a machine. In woodworking the term "circular saw" refers specifically to the hand-held type and the table saw and chop saw are other common forms of circular saws. "Skill saw" has become a generic trademark for conventional hand-held circular saws. Circular saw blades are specially designed for each particular material they are intended to cut and in cutting wood are specifically designed for making rip-cuts, cross-cuts, or a combination of both. Circular saws are commonly powered by electricity, but may be powered by a gasoline engine or a hydraulic motor which allows it to be fastened to heavy equipment, eliminating the need for a separate energy source [1].

1.7 Working Principle

The working of this manual timber sawing machine is mainly done by chain and sprocket mechanism. The machine consists of the pedal arrangement which rotates the larger sprocket in which the power is transmitted to the smaller sprocket. This mechanism is used to rotate the shaft connected to the smaller sprocket which is having an extended rod connected to a spur gear directly by means of a bearing support. Which gear is meshed with other spur gear on another shaft which is holding a circular saw. As the user operated the pedal, the circular saw cuts the various timber automatically with less power. This paper consists of a larger sprocket which rotates with a help of human powered pedal. The larger sprocket is connected with smaller sprocket with chain. The power circular saw machine which runs on human power, works on the principle of the conversion of rotational motion in a mutually perpendicular axis [3].

Fig 1.4: Chain and Sprocket Mechanism

1.8 Advantage and Disadvantage of Manual Timber Sawing Machine

Advantages:

1. It required no power for operation.
2. It is easy in maintenance.
3. It does not require any special skill for operation.
4. Cost of manually operated wood working machine is less than other machines because no source of electricity required.
5. Its construction is simple.
6. It is portable[1].
7. For working operations, it needs to work on machine at a time

Disadvantages:

1. It is time consuming process.
2. Sometimes some part can break.
3. Not fit for heavy production[1].

1.9 Applications of Manual Timber Sawing Machine

1. It can be used in small carpentry workshop.
2. It is use for cutting wood were power source not available.
3. In rural areas where electricity cut-off problems occur.
4. It is use for timber sawing operation[1].

1.10 Literature Review

Rahul C Meshram has done a paper on “Design and Fabrication of Manually Operated Wood Sawing Machine: Save Electric Power”. In this paper, design concept and fabrication of manually operated wood sawing/cutting machine is explained. It is designed and fabricated so portable that it can be move and used at various places[1].

Dhanasegaran A, et.al; have done a paper on “Design and Fabrication of Pedal Powered Circular Saw for Wood Working Applications. In this paper, the objective was using conventional mechanical plays a great role. In this paper, Pedal operated circular saw machine which can be used for industrial applications and household needs is fabricated. It does not require any specific input energy or electric power. The objective of this model is using the conventional mechanical process which plays a vital role[3].

Dr. R. A. Kubde, et.al; have done a paper on “Design and Fabrication of Manually Operated Wood Working Machine”. In this paper the machine operated by human peddling so no any other extra energy is needed. In the present work, a human powered multipurpose machine is developed which can perform three types of operations sawing and grinding. Power required for pedaling is above the capacity of an average healthy human being[5].

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Components of Manual Timber Sawing Machine

Pedal

A bicycle pedal is the part of a bicycle that the rider pushes with their foot to propel the bicycle. It provides the connection between the cyclists’ foot or shoe and the crank allowing the leg to turn the bottom bracket spindle

and propel the bicycle's wheels. Pedals were initially attached to cranks connecting directly to the driven (usually front) wheel. The safety bicycle, as it is known today, came into being when the pedals were attached to a crank driving a sprocket that transmitted power to the driven wheel by means of a roller chain. Pedals usually consist of a spindle that threads into the end of the crank and a body, on which the foot rests or is attached, that is free to rotate on bearings with respect to the spindle [3].

Fig 2.1: Pedal

Chain and Sprocket

Sprocket is the major component of this system because it is power transmitting device. It gets power from the chain drive and make this system to work. The chain drive belonged to drive with an intermediate link (flexible connection) which is represented by a chain. This drive uses an endless chain running around two sprocket It is the device which transmits the linear motion of meshing chain drive into rotary motion by means of the tooth found on it. The sprocket with ball bearing is said to be free wheel[3].

Fig 2.2: Chain

Fig 2.3: Sprocket

Circular Saw Blade

A circular saw blade is a power-saw using a toothed or abrasive disc or blade to cut different materials using a rotary motion spinning around an arbor. A whole saw and ring saw also use a rotary motion but are different from a circular saw. Circular saws may also be loosely used for the blade itself. Circular saws were invented in the late 18th century and were in common use in sawmills[3].

Fig 2.4: Circular Saw Blade

Seat

A bicycle seat, unlike a bicycle saddle, is designed to support the rider's buttocks and back, usually in a semi-reclined position. Arthur Graford is credited with inventing the padded bicycle seat in 1892, and they are now usually found on recumbent bicycles. Bicycle seats come in three main styles; mesh, hard shell and combination[3].

Fig 2.5: Seat

Bearing

A bearing is a machine element that constrains relative motion to only the desired motion, and reduces friction between moving parts. The design of the bearing may, for example, provide for free linear movement of the moving part; or, it may prevent a motion by controlling the vectors of normal forces that bear on the moving parts. Most bearing facilitate the desired motion by minimizing friction. Bearings are classified broadly according to the type of operation, the motions allowed, or to the directions of the loads (forces) applied to the parts[4].

Fig 2.6: Bearing

Shaft

A shaft is a rotating machine element which is used to transmit power from one place to another. The power is developed to the shaft by some tangential force and the resultant torque (or twisting moment) set up within the shaft permits the power to be transferred to various machines linked up to the shaft. In order to transfer the power from one shaft to another, the various members such as gear, pulleys etc. are mounted on it[1].

Fig 2.7: Shaft

Gear

Gear is a machine element which is used to transmit power from one shaft to other. There are many types of gear. Spur Gear ,Bevel gear , Worm Gear , Helical Gear. Here we use spur gear for changing the direction of the motion of shaft.

Fig 2.8: Spur Gear

Wood

Here we use wood for making frame on which the structure of sawing machine will stand. We also use wood for making the table and seat of the sawing machine.

Fig 2.9: Seat, Frame & Table.

Fig 2.10: Schematic Diagram of Manual Timber Sawing Machine

III. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Materials Need for Construction

For the construction of the manual timber sawing machine, I have used the materials given below

Table 3.1: Materials I have used for constructing Manual Timber Sawing Machine

Components name	Rating	Quantity
Metal (L Shaped)	Length 610*25*5 mm	2
	Length 545*25*5 mm	1
Metal (I Shaped)	Length 150*25*5 mm	2
	Length 130*25*5 mm	2

	Length 100*25*5 mm Length 545*25*5 mm Length 355*25*5 mm	1 2 1
Wood	Thickness 45mm, Width 45mm Thickness 50mm, Width 25mm Thickness 20mm,Width 20mm	As needed
Circular Sawing Machine	40 Teeth & 185 mm Diameter	1
Sprocket (Large)	48 Teeth	1
Sprocket (Small)	16 Teeth	1
Gear	21 Teeth	2
Shaft (Large)	Diameter 16mm & Length 455mm	1
Shaft (Small)	Diameter 16mm & Length 150mm	1
Bearing	Inner Diameter 15mm & Outer Diameter 38mm	4
Pedal	Length 90*70*30	2
Chain		1

3.1: Constructed Manual Timber Sawing Machine

Fig 3.2: Constructed Manual Timber Sawing Machine

For constructing Manual Timber Sawing Machine, I have used different kinds of operation. Those are given below:

- **Arc Welding**

I have used arc welding for joining two metals as I needed.

- **Gas Welding**

I have used gas welding for joining two spur gear with two shafts.

• **Drilling**

I have used lathe machine for drilling operation for making bush for the bearing, small sprocket and circular saw.

• **Hammering**

I have used a hand hammer for hammering operation to join two wood pieces by nails.

3.3 Calculation

Here on the manual Timber Sawing Machine,

The weight of circular saw is, $m=180\text{gm}=0.18\text{ kg}$

The radius of circular saw is, $r = 92.5\text{mm}=0.0925\text{m}$

Number of Teeth of Larger Sprocket, $T_1 = 48$

Number of Teeth of Smaller Sprocket, $T_2= 16$

Average r.p.m. given on larger sprocket, $N_1=80\text{ r.p.m}$ (measured)

Now the r.p.m transmitted on smaller sprocket = N_2

We know,

$$T_1/T_2=N_2/N_1$$

$$\Rightarrow N_2=3*80$$

Now, the rotation on smaller sprocket is, $N_2=240\text{ r.p.m}$

The two spur have same teeth. So, the rotation of smaller sprocket and the rotation of circular saw (N_s) is same.

$$N_s=240\text{ r.p.m}$$

The angular velocity of circular saw = $(2*3.1416*240)/60 = 25.1328\text{ rad/s}$

Now, the angular acceleration of circular saw, $\alpha = 25.1328/60=0.42\text{ rad/s}^2$

Now, Torque of the saw = $mr^2*\alpha =0.18*(0.0925)^2*0.42= 6.46 \times 10^{-4}\text{ Nm}$.

Force given by the circular saw blade on a wood=Torque/r = $(6.46 \times 10^{-4})/0.0925 =6.984 \times 10^{-3}\text{N}$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Performance Test

The circular saw of manual timber sawing machine gives $6.984*10^{-3}\text{ N}$ force to a timber piece.

With this tangential force it can cut many different types of timber pieces.

I have taken 4 different sample of timber pieces. And the dimension of all of those timber pieces is, Thickness = 15mm, Width = 42mm. I have cut at the width. So, I do not consider the length of the timber pieces.

- The machine can cut the **Mahogany** timber piece in **12 seconds**.
- The machine can cut the **Shirish** timber piece in **16 seconds**.
- The machine can cut the **Chambul** timber piece in **24 seconds**.
- The machine can cut **Kerosene** timber piece in **25 seconds**.

And the manual timber sawing machine can cut a timber piece of **45 mm** thickness at one chance.

Fig 4.1: Performance test of the Manual Timber Sawing Machine.

4.2 Result

The 4 sample of timber pieces are cut smoothly by my manual timber sawing machine.

4.3 Discussion

I have finished the construction of my paper on manual timber sawing machine. In this machine, human power is needed to give for running the machine. And that is by pedaling. It can cut smoothly all the timber pieces with circular saw blade. In this machine with the larger sprocket, a smaller sprocket is connected by a chain. By the rotation of larger sprocket, the smaller sprocket rotates. And with smaller sprocket a spur gear is connected by a shaft. And the spur gear is meshed with another spur gear which is connected by another shaft with circular saw. So, by giving clockwise rotation the circular saw gives anticlockwise rotation which is recommended for cutting a timber piece. In this manual timber sawing machine, the sample timber pieces are cut smoothly. But for human effort that means pedaling cannot give uniform rotational speed all the time. So, when I give much speed on the larger sprocket the timber cut quickly otherwise it takes more than before. Finally, the manual timber sawing machine is so comfortable to cut timber pieces.

V. CONCLUSION

The manual timber sawing machine I have constructed is very useful for rural area where there is no electricity. And it can also use at the time of load shedding in town area. It is a very low costing manual timber sawing machine which has easy operating system. The design is very simple for use. It reduces human effort than hand operated wood cutter. And one person can cut wood with this machine easily. And a person can cut wood comfortably for many times. So, it is a very comfortable machine also.

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